

SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES AS THE WAY TO INCREASE ASEAN COUNTRIES COMPETITIVENESS TO FACE ASEAN ECONOMIC COMMUNITY 2015

Mardhatilla Amalia, Accounting, University of Indonesia
Depok, Indonesia. mardhae@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

Analyzing the competitiveness of ASEAN countries while every country comes up as a country with difference identity, we should considerate on how to increase each countries' competitiveness to face ASEAN Economic Community 2015. The four characteristics for this AEC such as single market and production base, competitive region, integration to global economy, and equitable economic development should be prepared more for each of ASEAN members before being integrated toward this agreement. Special Economic Zones (SEZ) becomes one of the solutions offered for each ASEAN country to be implemented in their countries to increase their own competitiveness in order to be more successful in competing with other neighborhood countries. SEZ framework provides condition called "soft enabling environment" for such countries to be more focused in developing their potential into competitive advantage. While each country expands its competitive advantage by implementing SEZ, the AEC in 2015 will increase ASEAN performance as the new world leading economic potential since each country will unite to boost ASEAN economic growth. Implementing SEZ in every ASEAN countries aim to increase countries competitiveness to face ASEAN Economic Community (AEC) in forming ASEAN as the new world leading economy.

Keywords: ASEAN Countries, Special Economic Zones (SEZ), ASEAN Economic Community (AEC)

1. BACKGROUND

ASEAN countries including 10 countries obviously have their own potential and different output offered for international market even with the same type but different quality. This difference will make such collaboration need for ASEAN countries to unite to fulfill each other needs. Indonesia the third world most populous country with the total of Indonesia citizens reach as 237,424,363 people showed big opportunity for labor that Singapore might need.¹ While Thailand as the big cassava exporter, second largest exporter of gypsum, leading exporter of rice and a major exporter of shrimp, etc plays its role by exporting the product that coming from its countries². ASEAN countries have its own competitive advantage with different type of product or service that be able to fulfill or substitute each other.

ASEAN Economic Community (AEC) comes up as the solution to be in the association because of their will to hand in hand to develop economy, socio-cultural and political-security. Thus, to achieve the integrated of developed economy, sustained welfare and prosperity, they declare ASEAN Economic Community plan which provide ASEAN member a single market for goods and services and also production base between each member to be achieved at 2015. The importance of this integration is to make realization of economy stabilization with the following key characteristic namely a single market and production base, a highly competitive economic region, a region of equitable economic development, and a region fully integrated into the global economy. It must become an important role in the world nowadays to develop their welfare by integrated with another country. The integration of ASEAN community means that in this huge growth of global environment with interdependent markets and globalised industries, ASEAN should take actions to build the competitiveness to become stronger and play a big role in global supply chain with each members' competitive advantage.

ASEAN countries with their own competitive advantage should be more prepared on the development of its own potential such as natural resources development, technology development to face the AEC 2015 in order not to sink in with the liberalization and globalized competition offered by AEC implementation.

¹ (<http://www.tradingeconomics.com/thailand/exports,2012>)

² (<http://worldpopulationreview.com/population-of-indonesia-2012/>)

Special Economic Zones provides a framework for ASEAN countries to be more focused on their development toward AEC 2015. An SEZ is an enclave of enterprises operating in a well-defined geographic area where certain economic activities are promoted by a set of policy measures that are not generally applicable to the rest of the country. This SEZ framework will help ASEAN countries to implement streamlined regulatory enforcement such as immediate access to high quality infrastructure, clearly titled land, facilities, and support services to create framework as “soft enabling environment” to attract investor to come to this each ASEAN countries in order to boost its economic performances. These special economic zones have created several success stories among several countries especially China, India, Pakistan, Malaysia and other nations. While ASEAN countries prepare themselves to expand its quality with Special Economic Zones, it will help ASEAN come up as the new leading potential economic with AEC.

The aim of this paper is trying to provide a picture on how ASEAN will implement SEZ to develop the competitiveness toward ASEAN Economic Community. How SEZ can help ASEAN Countries develop its competitive advantage? What have been SEZ key drivers to develop ASEAN countries toward AEC? This paper is emerged with some basic strategies and information aim to provide some recommendation for ASEAN countries to prepare their own capability to face AEC agreement and come up as the world new leading economy.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Research Model

This study based on some theoretical perspective³ that measure country competitiveness based on government support, industrial structure/cluster strategy, innovation policy, infrastructure, bureaucracy and the important variable of doing business. In figure 1 a research model which consist of three building block. The right block represent Doing Business indicators (2012) which indicate that there are 10 important indicators of SEZ competitiveness: Starting a business, Dealing with construction permits, Employing workers, Registering property, Getting credit, Protecting investors, Paying taxes, Trading across borders, Enforcing contracts, Resolving

³ (see Porter 2008, CSF, 2007; Wahyuni, et al. 2009)

insolvency (formerly recognised as closing business). The second and the third blocks are the soft enabling environment which will be the key indicator for ASEAN countries to develop its potential to face ASEAN Economic Community 2015.

Figure 1. Research Model

Sources: Competitiveness of Special Economic Zones, 2012

2.2 Special Economic Zones

Special Economic Zone (SEZ) is an enclave of enterprises operating in a well-defined geographic area where certain economic activities are promoted by a set of policy measures that are not generally applicable to the rest of the country. Some of the key characteristics of successful zones are that they offer immediate access to high quality infrastructures, clearly titled land, facilities, and support services. In addition, streamlined regulatory enforcement, simpler business establishment rules, expedited customs administration, and other special administrative and approval procedures are also offered in such zones.⁴ Those characteristics are related to regional competitiveness.

Figure 1. SEZ Competitiveness Model

Sources: Competitiveness of Special Economic Zones, 2012

⁴ (Competitiveness Support Fund, 2007; Wahyuni et al., 2010).

Figure 2. Porter Diamond on Competitiveness

Sources: Competitiveness of Special Economic Zones, 2012

2.3 ASEAN Economic Community (AEC) 2015

Asean Economy Community (AEC) is the new way purposed by ASEAN countries regarding for the recent fenomenon happened and the most spoken issues such as free trade. Economy integration is required to accomplish greater economy size. The ASEAN economies will have responded the competition among the society by trading in goods, trade in services and investments. AEC will give a great contribution in state of economy growth by facilitating trade and inducing investment, equitable economic development, and single market and production base. Whether to intensify the initiative of new cooperation and the implementation are accelerated the integration of single market and production base, which will make a wider global supply chain.⁵

⁵ ASEAN (2008), *Declaration of The ASEAN Economic Community Blueprint*. (www.asean.org)

Figure 3. Asean Economy Community Blueprint

Source: Asean Economy Community Blueprint, 2008 (organised)

There are some characteristics of AEC⁶ such as:

1) Single Market and Production Based

a. Free flow of goods

Free flow of goods is one of the principal means by which the aims of a single market and production base can be achieved. A single market for goods (and services) will also facilitate the development of production networks in the region and enhance ASEAN's capacity to serve as a global production centre or as a part of the global supply chain. (ASEAN Blueprint, 2008)

There are some characteristic for free flow of goods such as elimination of tariffs; elimination of non-tariff barriers; rules of origin (ROO); trade facilitation; customs integration; ASEAN Single Window; Standards and Technical Barriers to Trade; Systems of standards; quality assurance, accreditation, and measurement are crucial to promote greater efficiency and enhance cost effectiveness of production of intra-regional imports/exports.

b. Free flow of services.

Free flow of trade in services is one of the important elements in realising ASEAN Economic Community, where there will be substantially no restriction to ASEAN services suppliers in providing services and in establishing companies across national borders within the

⁶ ASEAN (2008), *Declaration of The ASEAN Economic Community Blueprint*. (www.asean.org)

region, subject to domestic regulations. Liberalisation of services has been carried out through rounds of negotiation mainly under the Coordinating Committee on Services.

c. Free flow of investment

A free and open investment regime is key to enhancing ASEAN's competitiveness in attracting foreign direct investment (FDI) as well as intra-ASEAN investment.

Sustained inflows of new investments and reinvestments will promote and ensure dynamic development of ASEAN economies.

d. Freer flow of capital

Strengthening ASEAN Capital Market Development and Integration.

e. Free flow of skilled labour

f. Priority Integration Sectors

g. Food, Agriculture and Forestry

2. Competitive Economic Region

a. Competition Policy

b. Consumer Protection

c. Intellectual property rights (IPR)

d. Infrastructure Development

e. Taxation

f. E-Commerce

3. Equitable Economic Development

a. SME development

b. Initiative for ASEAN Integration (IAI)

4. Integration into the Global Economy

a. Coherent Approach towards External Economic Relations

b. Enhanced participation in global supply networks

3. ANALYSIS

3.1 ASEAN Countries Competitiveness with Special Economic Zones (SEZs)

Analyzing ASEAN economies, it can be shown by doing business indicator from World Bank like the Research Model above explained (Literature Review). Here are the tables for ASEAN Countries Doing Business⁷:

Table1. Doing Business in Brunei Darussalam

TOPIC RANKINGS	DB 2013 Rank	DB 2012 Rank	Change in Rank
Starting a Business	135	137	↑ 2
Dealing with Construction Permits	43	88	↑ 45
Getting Electricity	29	29	No change
Registering Property	115	113	↑ -2
Getting Credit	129	127	↑ -2
Protecting Investors	117	114	↑ -3
Paying Taxes	22	21	↑ -1
Trading Across Borders	40	36	↑ -4
Enforcing Contracts	158	158	No change
Resolving Insolvency	46	44	↑ -2

Sources: Doing Business 2012 and 2013

Table 2. Doing Business in Malaysia

TOPIC RANKINGS	DB 2013 Rank	DB 2012 Rank	Change in Rank
Starting a Business	54	42	↑ -12
Dealing with Construction Permits	96	116	↑ 20
Getting Electricity	28	27	↑ -1
Registering Property	33	62	↑ 29
Getting Credit	1	1	No change
Protecting Investors	4	4	No change
Paying Taxes	15	25	↑ 10
Trading Across Borders	11	12	↑ 1
Enforcing Contracts	33	31	↑ -2
Resolving Insolvency	49	48	↑ -1

Sources: Doing Business 2012 and 2013

⁷ World Bank (2012), “Doing Business China 2012: Doing Business in More Transparent World,” The International Bank for Reconstruction and Development.

Table 3. Doing Business in Indonesia

TABLE 1.3 Best practices in Indonesia compared internationally			
Indicator	Best performing city within Indonesia	Performance	Global rank (183 economies) How Indonesia would compare globally
Number of procedures to deal with construction permits	Medan, Yogyakarta	7 procedures	4
Days to deal with construction permits	Banda Aceh	42 days	5
Days to register property	Manado	12 days	27
Cost to deal with construction permits	Jambi	32% of income per capita	42
Number of procedures to register property	All cities except Batam, Semarang	6 procedures	83
Number of procedures to start a business	Balikpapan, Denpasar, Jakarta, Palangka Raya, Surakarta, Yogyakarta	8 procedures	109
Cost to start a business	Jakarta, Pontianak, Yogyakarta	18% of income per capita	111
Days to start a business	Gorontalo, Palangka Raya	27 days	117
Cost to register property	Jakarta	10.81% of property value	151

Source: Doing Business database.

Sources: Doing Business 2012 and 2013

Table 4. Doing Business in Thailand

TOPIC RANKINGS	DB 2013 Rank	DB 2012 Rank	Change in Rank
Starting a Business	85	79	+ -6
Dealing with Construction Permits	16	13	+ -3
Getting Electricity	10	9	+ -1
Registering Property	26	27	+ 1
Getting Credit	70	67	+ -3
Protecting Investors	13	13	No change
Paying Taxes	96	92	+ -4
Trading Across Borders	20	20	No change
Enforcing Contracts	23	26	+ 3
Resolving Insolvency	58	52	+ -6

Sources: Doing Business 2012 and 2013

Table 5. Doing Business in Philippines

TOPIC RANKINGS	DB 2013 Rank	DB 2012 Rank	Change in Rank
Starting a Business	161	158	↓ -3
Dealing with Construction Permits	100	101	↑ 1
Getting Electricity	57	53	↑ -4
Registering Property	122	120	↑ -2
Getting Credit	129	127	↑ -2
Protecting Investors	128	124	↑ -4
Paying Taxes	143	136	↑ -7
Trading Across Borders	53	56	↑ 3
Enforcing Contracts	111	109	↑ -2
Resolving Insolvency	165	166	↑ 1

Sources: Doing Business 2012 and 2013

Table 6. Doing Business in Singapore

TOPIC RANKINGS	DB 2013 Rank	DB 2012 Rank	Change in Rank
Starting a Business	4	4	No change
Dealing with Construction Permits	2	2	No change
Getting Electricity	5	6	↑ 1
Registering Property	36	36	No change
Getting Credit	12	9	↑ -3
Protecting Investors	2	2	No change
Paying Taxes	5	4	↑ -1
Trading Across Borders	1	1	No change
Enforcing Contracts	12	13	↑ 1
Resolving Insolvency	2	2	No change

Sources: Doing Business 2012 and 2013

Table 7. Doing Business in Laos

TOPIC RANKINGS	DB 2013 Rank	DB 2012 Rank	Change in Rank
Starting a Business	81	93	↑ 12
Dealing with Construction Permits	87	80	↓ -7
Getting Electricity	138	131	↓ -7
Registering Property	74	71	↓ -3
Getting Credit	167	165	↓ -2
Protecting Investors	184	184	No change
Paying Taxes	126	122	↓ -4
Trading Across Borders	160	162	↑ 2
Enforcing Contracts	114	113	↓ -1
Resolving Insolvency	185	185	No change

Sources: Doing Business 2012 and 2013

Table 8. Doing Business in Vietnam

TOPIC RANKINGS	DB 2013 Rank	DB 2012 Rank	Change in Rank
Starting a Business	108	109	↑ 1
Dealing with Construction Permits	28	27	↓ -1
Getting Electricity	155	157	↑ 2
Registering Property	48	48	No change
Getting Credit	40	38	↓ -2
Protecting Investors	169	167	↓ -2
Paying Taxes	138	153	↑ 15
Trading Across Borders	74	74	No change
Enforcing Contracts	44	41	↓ -3
Resolving Insolvency	149	145	↓ -4

Sources: Doing Business 2012 and 2013

Table 9. Doing Business in Cambodia

TOPIC RANKINGS	DB 2013 Rank	DB 2012 Rank	Change in Rank
Starting a Business	175	174	+ -1
Dealing with Construction Permits	149	147	+ -2
Getting Electricity	132	128	+ -4
Registering Property	115	114	+ -1
Getting Credit	53	97	+ 44
Protecting Investors	82	79	+ -3
Paying Taxes	66	61	+ -5
Trading Across Borders	118	121	+ 3
Enforcing Contracts	142	144	+ 2
Resolving Insolvency	152	152	No change

Sources: Doing Business 2012 and 2013

This doing business tables show that the comparison between doing business in ASEAN Countries from 2012 until 2013. There are some indicators that make the rank of ASEAN countries decrease and increase from the previous year. This table will give us the big picture that the condition in ASEAN countries still need to be developed in order to compete in free trade area or in this case AEC which will indicate single market with high competitive region. First step to improve the condition in ASEAN countries in order to increase ASEAN performance is by implementing SEZ in order to be able to has equitable market economic growth also to be integrated to face global economy.

3.2 Benchmarking to China with Successful SEZ Implementation to Increase Country Competitiveness

Remarkable economic growth has been spotlight China as the potential world economic leader. China is the world's second largest economy after overtaking Japan in 2010. China has been succeed to have GDP real growth for 10,3 % in 2010 and reached GDP per capita to US\$7,400 (CIA World Fact Book 2011). A major component supporting China's rapid economy growth is the enermous growing of exports. This positive skewed graphic economy of China has trigger some countries to questioned and analyzed what is exactly happening in China and how this country reached numerous increase growth in their financial sector. SEZ becomes significantly to national GDP, employment, exports and attraction of foreign investment and new technologies. SEZ has been contributed 5% 5% of China's total real GDP in 2006, 22% of total merchandise exports and 9% of total FDI inflows. At the same time, the 54 national SEZ accounted for 5% of total GDP, 15% of exports and 22% of total FDI inflow as

the following table shows. China's special economic zones also contribute 50,000 invention patents in total, more than 70% of which were registered by domestic firms (Zhong et al., 2009). 54 SEZs hosted about half the national high-tech firms, and science and technology incubators in 2007.

Table 10. Performance of China Initial Five SEZ, National Economic, and Technological Zone, 2006

Indicator	SEZs	National ETDZs	China
Total employment (millions) as % of China total	15	4	758
	2.0	0.5	100
Real GDP (RMB of 100 millions) as % of China total	9,101	8,145	183,085
	5.0	4.5	100
Utilized FDI (US\$100 millions) as % of China total	55	130	603
	9.1	21.6	100
Merchandise exports (US\$100 millions) as % of China total	1,686	1,138	7,620
	22.1	14.9	100
Total population (millions) as % of China total	15	–	1,038
	1.9	–	100

Source: National Statistic Bureau, 2006.

Note: – = not available (n.a.).

3.3 Macro View for Special Economic Zones in ASEAN Countries towards ASEAN Economic Community (AEC)

The above explanation has been elaborated that special economic zones have been significantly develop the country competitiveness. This made that ASEAN countries will be able to be more focus on its developing its competitive advantages by implementing special economic zones framework.

While these ASEAN countries increase its own competitiveness, it will increase the ASEAN Community Economic to face the global competition through this process.

Figure 3. Implementation SEZ in ASEAN Countries toward AEC

Sources: Writers

The above process will lead to the AEC future that will impact all ASEAN Country economic growth. ASEAN economic growth keep showing the increasing point year by year as the following graphic showed. Based on the projection in 2012 by International Monetary Fund, the GDP will increase more than 2% for ASEAN countries. ASEAN economies including Indonesia, the Philippines, Singapore, and Thailand, the lower current account balances reflected mainly a welcome increase in investment-to-GDP ratios which hopefully might help strengthen domestic sources of growth in a more sustainable way. Overall, the progress made across the region is important and can be built on with continued reforms in the coming years. This promising data show how bright the future of SEAN economic for the next few years. Compared to Asia's current account surplus, this growth will be expected to bottom out in 2012, at just above 1½ percent of regional GDP, and then increase to just below 2 percent in 2013.

Figure 4. Selected Asia: Current Account Balances

4. Conclusion

The implementation of Special Economic Zones will boost up ASEAN Countries competitiveness in order to be able to compete in ASEAN Economic Community for 2005. This Special Economic Zones framework will intend to increase Doing Business Performance of ASEAN Countries in order to come up as integrated world leading economy with AEC platform.

REFERENCES

- Wahyuni, Sari. (2012). *Competitiveness of Special Economic Zone: Comparison between Indonesia, Malaysia, Thailand, and China*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- World Bank (2013), *Doing Business China 2011: Making a Difference for Entrepreneurs*, The International Bank for Reconstruction and Development.
- World Bank (2012), “*Doing Business China 2012: Doing Business in More Transparant World*,” The International Bank for Reconstruction and Development.
- ASEAN (2010), *ASEAN Economic Community Scorecard*. (www.asean.org)
- ASEAN (2008), *Declaration of The ASEAN Economic Community Blueprint*. (www.asean.org)
- ASEAN (2009), *Roadmap ASEAN Economic Community 2015*. ASEAN Annual Report 2008-2009 (www.asean.org)
- Ministry of Finance Government of Pakistan. (2007). *Special Economic Zone Benchmarking and Policy Action Plan*. Competitiveness Support Fund.
- Guo, Wanda and Yueqiu Feng. (2007). *Special Economic Zones and Competitiveness*. Asian Development Bank.
- Zeng, Douglas Zhihua. (2011). *How Do Special Economic Zones and Industrial Clusters Drive China’s Rapid Development?*. The World Bank Africa Region, Finance & Private Sectors Development.
- FIAS. (2008). *Special Economic Zones Perfomance, Lessons, Leaned, and Implications for Zone Development*. The World Bank Group.
- Aggarwal, Aradhna, etc. (2007). *Special Economic Zones in South Asia: Industrial Islands or Vehicles for Diversification?*. International Trade Department, The World Bank.
- ESCAP. (2005). *Best practices and policy guidelines:7 Best practices and policy guidelines*. United Nation (<http://www.unescap.org>)
- Schweinberger, Albert G. (2003). *Special Economic Zones in Developing and/or Transition Economies: a Policy Proposal*. Review of International Economics, 11, 4:619–629.
- Juan, LI Hui. (2000). *Knowledge Transfer from Foreign Affiliates to China*. School of Economics and Management, Henan Polytechnic University.